
PROJECT DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Document data

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable D9.4 – Data Management Plan – establishes the framework under which Agro-Serv consortium will generate, process and collect data during project's activities including the implementation of TNA projects.

D9.4 details as well how the data will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use and how the data will be curated and preserved after the project is completed.

This current document corresponds to the first version of the Agro-Serv Data Management Plan (DMP), therefore composed by preliminary information and frameworks that will be followed and potentially updated, in the near future, to collect and characterise project's data sets (which will be presented in next iterations of the current deliverable). Moreover, the DMP details the standards that will be used, how the research data will be preserved and what data sets will be published for verification or reuse as open access. The DMP covers the entire research data life cycle and must be consistent with exploitation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) requirements. Hence, research data linked to exploitable results will not be put into the open domain if they compromise the consortium's commercialisation prospects or have inadequate protection.

Sensitive and/or personal data provided by consortium partners for the TNA implementation and personal data of the users will be kept strictly confidential and anonymized, i.e., secured in a way to maintain compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Information herein presented goes beyond Agro-Serv's Grant and Consortium Agreement, stating the progress that was achieved within the first six months of the project in what concerns Data Management methodologies.

This document has been built based on the Horizon 2020 FAIR DMP template (Version: 26 July 2016), which promotes the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" together with the project ambition of "Open by Default".

The first section of the document presents the deliverable and contextualises it within the Agro-Serv project.

The second section provides a description for the characterisation of the data sets to be generated by the project and how the data will be generated/acquired, processed and archived.

The third section of this deliverable is devoted to ethics, privacy and security considerations to ensure compliance with European and national legislation as well as directives relevant to the country where the data collection would take place. This includes that the collection, processing and transmission of personal data will be analysed under principles of: (a) the GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)90; (b) the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Convention 108 for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data; and (c) the national laws applying its provisions. All beneficiaries are

informed about consent-giving, data processing, data security, and the pertinent regulations such as GDPR which are addressed in the third section.

The DMP is concluded, in section 4, by outlining the guidelines how the data is archived and preserved for long-term beyond the project's conclusion.

Glossary

Term	Description
Agro-Serv	The present project
DMP	Data Management Plan, i.e. the present document.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier, a proprietary PID managed by the International DOI Foundation (IDF), a not-for-profit membership organisation that is the governance and management body for the federation of Registration Agencies providing Digital Object Identifier (DOI) services and registration, and is the registration authority for the ISO standard (ISO 26324) for the DOI system.
DPO	Data Protection Officer, a data management expert who ensures, in an independent manner, that an organisation applies the laws protecting individuals' personal data. The role, responsibilities, and organisational position of the DPO are described in Articles 37, 38, and 39 of the GDPR.
ENVRI	ENVRI is a community of environmental Research infrastructures working together to observe the Earth as one system.
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud is a European Commission initiative aiming at developing an infrastructure providing its users with services promoting open science practices
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures, a European Strategic Instrument tasked with developing the scientific integration of Europe and to strengthen its international outreach.
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable. This acronym identifies a set of properties scientific data assets should possess to enable reproducible research and thus to be relevant to the research community.
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation, the EU law that establishes the legal framework for personal data management
PID	Persistent Identifier; a long-lasting reference to a digital resource. An identifier is a label which gives a unique name to

	an entity: a person, place, or thing. Unlike URLs, which may break, a persistent identifier reliably points to a digital entity.
TNA	Trans-National Access. Allowing third party researchers from a foreign institution to access an organisation's research facilities and services.
VA	Virtual Access. Allowing third-party researchers to access an organisation's cloud, datacenter, and/or its other IT facilities and services.
VRE	Virtual Research Environment. A IT service designed to enable researchers to design and execute experiments in an integrated fashion.
WP	Work Package. A set of related activities within a project.

1 Introduction

The present document serves as Data and Management Plan for the Agro-Serv project, and as such it outlines policies, principles, and best practices which have a transversal impact across multiple project activities. Due to the volatile and ever-evolving nature of the digital landscape, this document is highly prone to change to include in the consortium policies new best practices and technologies as they emerge, therefore it is of vital importance to establish a change management framework as well. In this Chapter we provide an overview of the document's goals, relationships with other activities, and change management plan.

1.1 Objective and scope

The current deliverable D9.4 – Data Management Plan – constitutes a guideline complying to European and national legislation on the acquiring, handling, processing and archiving of data generated during the Agro-Serv project and beyond the project's end, being updated by Month 24 and 36. D9.4 allows for a consortium-wide alignment around the project's data management processes. The objective is to promote the principles of:

1. FAIR data management and stewardship as described in the paper [“The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship” \(2016\)](#);
2. the GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679);
3. the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Convention 108 for the Protection of Individuals according to Automatic Processing of Personal Data;
4. the national laws applying its provisions.

Although Agro-Serv will not manage all data assets directly, this document establishes a set of guidelines and best practices individual TNAs & VAs are expected to comply with in their data management activities.

More specifically, each TNA and VA applicant is expected to provide the Agro-Serv consortium with detailed information on its data management activities, which have to be consistent with the policies outlined in the present document.

1.2 Relation to other activities

As other WP 9 deliverables, the DMP has a transversal actuation throughout Agro-Serv, providing a guideline on how partners should generate, acquire, handle, share, and curate research data during all activities carried out within and beyond Agro-Serv and its TNA and VA projects.

The DMP will be made publicly available to ensure that the whole consortium is aware of the practices that shall be followed within the conduction of those activities.

TNA applicants are expected to read the present document and to conform to the herein described policies upon planning their data management activities.

The Agro-Serv consortium is participating in the development of the ISIA web application that will integrate the cross-cutting requirements of project assessment, compliance with TNA obligations, ethical rules and data management into the project intake process.

After validation of the evaluation steps, the recommendations concerning the TNA, ethics and data management will be distributed to the platforms concerned by each project to ensure the follow-up of their implementation.

1.3 DMP Change Management

Agro-Serv and its participants acknowledge how the data and IT services environment is evolving at a steady pace as Information Technology is rapidly becoming not only enabling, but essential to research.

Agro-Serv and its participants are committed to offer TNA projects a level of service that is not only up to date with industry standards, but also fully compliant with EU laws and best practices in scientific data management. As regulations and best practices are prone to change, Agro-Serv acknowledges that Data Management policies may need to change over the course of the project and therefore the need to establish a framework to enable effective change management.

The DMP will undergo two scheduled revisions during which a DMP committee will be formed by WP3 and WP9 and implement timely the following steps:

1. **Identification of change requests:** in the event of (i) new data management requirements being imposed by external requirement providers or (ii) emerging new data management requirements brought up by consortium members, the DMP committee will identify which parts of the present document will be impacted by the new requirement, evaluate their implementation urgency and feasibility within the DMP update schedule.
2. **DMP change specification:** the DMP committee will design, for each change request, new and adequate procedures, and draft a candidate DMP revision.

3. **Pilot:** a data item impacted by the change, thereby including a data asset, a data service, or a Web service will be managed under the new DMP draft's regulations for an adequate time. The pilot is defined on a voluntary basis, i.e. the item's owner must be aware of the pilot's goals and extents, and willing to cooperate to the success of the pilot, thereby including the provision of adequate feedback. WP 9 will oversee and coordinate the Pilot phase.
4. **Change implementation:** after a successful pilot, the DMP will be updated and the new management procedures will become executive.

Agro-Serv identifies the EU, the ESFRI community, the EOSC association, and projects funded under the INFRA-EOSC initiative as external requirement providers, i.e. non-consortium organisations who can establish new data management requirements. The two scheduled DMP revisions are expected to become executive respectively by month 24 and 36.

In the unlikely event of disruptive external change requests requiring immediate response, WP3 and WP9 reserve themselves the right to perform extraordinary DMP revisions which may skip the pilot phase and become immediately executive. In such an unlikely case, the consortium will be promptly and adequately informed of the ongoing DMP revision activities.

2 Data Summary

In this Chapter we describe the various types of data Agro-Serv will handle during its operational period. Some assets will be managed directly by the Agro-Serv WPs, while others will be managed by TNA projects independently, however, for the purpose of general data management, each discrete data asset should fall in one of the categories described in the present chapter and be treated accordingly.

2.1 Grant applications

TNA Grant applications are an essential part of the Agro-Serv project, as they represent a mandatory preliminary phase to the establishment of a TNA grant agreement between the consortium and the applicant.

Each grant application describes in detail a transnational research activity (TNA) that may take place during the project's course and its expected results.

The contents of a grant application are confidential between the applicant and the consortium and should not be divulged under any circumstance except under explicit agreement between the applicant and Agro-Serv.

Grant applications are managed in the ISIA application¹ according to the ethical principles and policies detailed in Chapter 4 of this document.

¹ <https://isia.cnrs.fr/>

2.2 Research Data

We identify as Research data all the data necessary to:

- a) evaluate the quantitative KPIs of the project and its funded TNA projects;
- b) validate the results presented in public deliverables and/or scientific publications.

The consortium strongly believes in and applies the concepts of open science and will actively promote the publication of Research Data according to the FAIR principles. TNA grant beneficiaries are expected to publish all research data they created, curated, or processed within their TNA activities by the end of the Agro-Serv project, unless specific exclusion criterias are met.

Chapter 3 of this document details the Agro-Serv policies concerning FAIR data publication and its exclusion criterias.

2.3 Observational and Operational Data

We identify as Observational and Operational data all the data, raw data generated/acquired as well as curated data during the TNA projects activities (operational data), and data from qualitative activities including surveys, interviews, fieldwork data or engagement activities (observational data).

These data assets will be managed by TNA grant beneficiaries according to their own data management practices and Agro-Serv considers them property of the TNA beneficiaries. As long as the management of said assets does not violate the general ethical guidelines presented in D 9.3, TNA beneficiaries have full discretionality on planning, implementing, and altering their management policies.

These data assets may, however, contain sensitive data provided by consortium partners and/or TNA grant beneficiaries and personal data of individual stakeholders. In such a case, Agro-Serv recommends keeping such assets strictly confidential to protect their owners' interests and privacy and declines every responsibility in the event of unauthorised publication or other data breach.

2.4 Documentation

Agro-Serv will handle several documental data assets other than Grant Applications, including, but not limited to, technical reports, scientific papers, documental deliverables, meeting minutes, manuals, spreadsheets, and presentation slides.

As a general rule, the Agro-Serv consortium won't disclose any documentation to third parties unless:

- Part of a Research Data asset and/or functional to the evaluation of a Project/TNA project KPI and/or to the reproducibility of a research result. In such a case the Research Data policies detailed in Section 2.2 will apply.
- Explicitly required in the context of the dissemination and exploitation strategy outlined in the Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement, and/or requested by the Communication, dissemination and IP management Board (WP8 and 9).
- Explicitly required to fulfil contractual and legal obligations.

These general rules however do not prevent asset owners from disclosing. In such a case, the Agro-Serv consortium will decline any responsibility on the confidentiality of the documentation and/or excerpts of it.

2.5 Source code

Agro-Serv and its related projects may develop source code assets. To the extent of the Agro-Serv project, these assets are considered as documentation and therefore will be treated with the same policies described in Section 2.4 .

3 FAIR Data

In this section we outline the Agro-Serv policies and best practices concerning FAIR publication of Research Data assets.

Agro-Serv is committed to the publication of Research Data according to the FAIR principles. Agro-Serv applies, for working purposes, the definitions of the FAIR principles provided by the GoFair Initiative², which are tailored towards EOSC compatibility.

Agro-Serv will build its FAIR enabling practices on the following resources provided by the European research community:

- FAIRsharing³: A curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata standards, inter-related to databases and data policies.
- FAIR cookbook⁴: a collection of recipes on the FAIR components, the infrastructure needed, and a set of applied examples in the Life Sciences, offering a deep dive in technical aspects of FAIR data management.
- RDM toolkit⁵: an archive of best practices and guidelines.
- The ENVRI training portal⁶: a collection of training materials for researchers and practitioners in the field of ecological sciences.

The management principles detailed in this Section apply to Research Data only, as the other categories of data assets are not subject to compulsory FAIR publication.

² <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

³ <https://fairsharing.org/>

⁴ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/>

⁵ <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

⁶ <https://training.envri.eu/>

3.1 General Principles

As a general rule, the Agro-Serv consortium expects Research Data publication to be done:

- according to the FAIR principles;
- in compliance with the Agro-Serv Research Data publication policy outlined in Section 3.1.1.

TNA applicants are expected to include in their application a Data Management Plan, providing indications on how they intend to comply with the above expectations.

The Agro-Serv consortium is aware that some data repositories may impose specific internal policies on PIDs, metadata formats, data accessibility, and data formats; in general, the consortium regards these constraints are acceptable as long as they do not violate the ethical principles detailed in Chapter 4 of the present document, and in D9.3.

3.1.1 Research Data Publication Policy

The Agro-Serv policy for data publication follows the H2020 Guidelines to Open Access. It is the will and commitment of the partners to share non-commercially sensitive knowledge and experience with the research community to ensure learning is transferred and errors are not repeated.

The general policy for managing data assets publication is the following:

- Research Data assets will be published if and only if they do not include data which divulgation may harm its owner (e.g. commercially sensitive data) or non-anonymized personal data. If the personal data therein cannot be anonymized in any way, the data asset will be published only if all the data subjects will give explicit and verifiable consent to publication.
- Research Data assets tied to a scientific publication will be published at the same time of the article publication unless a grace period is explicitly requested by the publication authors and/or data asset owners and/or copyright holders and/or other stakeholders.
- Any Research Data asset eligible for publication will be published by the end of the project.

TNA applicants have the liberty of deciding publication details on their own, including the publication venue, but they have to comply with the above described policies when planning data publication.

3.1.2 Exclusions and Grace Periods

Research Data assets that meet one or more of the following criteria are not eligible for publication:

- Data divulgation could be harmful for the EU and/or the owner organisation and/or physical persona. Data divulgation can be considered harmful when clearly against the data owner's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or clearly present a violation of other constraints, notably the EU competitive interests or the data owner's obligations under the Agro-Serv Grant Agreement.

- Data contains non-anonymized personal data and data subjects did not consent to publication and/or their consent cannot be verified.

Research Data owners can tie their data assets to a publication, in such a case the Agro-Serv consortium should be informed of the publication’s due date and optionally of a grace period extent. The Grace period cannot be more than 1 year and when not communicated, Agro-Serv will assume it is not requested.

Research Data assets with no grace period will be published at the same time of their tied publication and the Agro-Serv consortium internally will refer to them as Gold Publication, while data assets with a grace period will be labelled as Green Publication.

The Agro-Serv policy on research data publication is summarised in the following figure.

Therefore, there are four possible publication options: no publication, publication within the end of the project, “gold” publication (i.e. with no grace period), and “green” publication (i.e. with grace period).

TNA applicants are expected to specify in their Data Management Plan, for each planned research data asset, the publication option they intend to adopt, and, in case of no publication, provide the consortium with evidence of the applicability of the above described exclusion criteria.

3.1.3 Acceptable Repositories

TNA applicants are expected to specify in their application's Data Management Plan their venue of choice for research data publication, and the Agro-Serv consortium will assume they will adopt the FAIR policies enforced by the venue.

In general, Agro-Serv promotes data publication through well known repositories such as Zenodo, Dryad, OSF, and several others.

A collection of well-known domain-specific and general-purpose repositories which will be considered as acceptable data publication venues by the Agro-Serv project is being curated and it will be published on FAIRsharing. We refer to the venues thereby included as *Acceptable Repositories* in the remainder of the chapter.

If the venue of choice does not enforce specific FAIRness policies and/or is not one of the Acceptable Repositories and/or the TNA applicants opt for a self-hosted research data publication, they are supposed to provide additional detail about their planned FAIRness-related actions, more specifically their Data Management Plan would need to include explicit indications of how they plan to make their data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable over time, in compliance with the consortium policies outlined in the remainder of this Chapter.

3.2 Making data findable

The Agro-Serv consortium acknowledges the primary importance of data findability: if a data asset is not findable, for practical purposes it does not exist. The consortium is therefore committed to enforcing data findability.

3.2.1 Persistent Identifiers

All Research Data assets produced within the Agro-Serv project must be associated upon publication with a persistent and dereferenceable identifier.

Agro-Serv does not enforce a specific PID format as long as the data asset is hosted on one of the Acceptable Repositories, however TNA applicants opting for a different hosting solution are expected to associate a DOI to each of their published research data assets.

The choice of the DOI as recommended PID is motivated by its adoption by the ENVRI community.

3.2.2 Rich Metadata

All Research Data assets produced within the Agro-Serv project must be associated upon publication with appropriate metadata to allow their inclusion in catalogues and appropriate indexing.

Agro-Serv does not enforce a specific PID format as long as the data asset is hosted on one of the Acceptable Repositories, however TNA applicants opting for a different hosting solution are expected to associate appropriate DCAT AP metadata to each of their published research data assets.

3.2.3 Cataloguing and Indexing

The Agro-Serv consortium aims at maximising the visibility, outreach, and impact of all research assets produced during the project, therefore research data assets produced within the Agro-Serv project will be included in data catalogues owned by consortium partners and stakeholders.

TNA applicants must be aware that their published Research Data assets may be included in a number of catalogues including, but not limited to, the EOSC marketplace, the ENVRI-Hub, FAIDARE, and the AnaEE data portal.

3.3 Making data Accessible

The Agro-Serv consortium acknowledges the importance of data accessibility: if a data asset cannot be accessed, it cannot be integrated and/or reused in any way. The consortium is therefore committed to enforcing data accessibility.

3.3.1 Data Access

All research data assets produced within the Agro-Serv project must be published in such a way that they are accessible. As a general rule, Agro-Serv will consider as accessible all Research Data assets exposed through one or more of the Acceptable Repositories.

TNA beneficiaries opting for different solutions are expected to provide in the TNA data management plan detailed indications of how they intend to make their assets accessible. Agro-Serv will consider Accessible an asset if and only if its contents can be accessed through a URL by means of well known internet protocols.

Therefore the following data access methods will be considered acceptable:

- Direct file download from a public URL, with or without prior user authentication.
- Programmatic access administered through an adequately documented RESTful API residing on a public URL, with or without prior user authentication. API documentation must include OpenAPI and/or GraphQL specification. API access can be subject to bandwidth and/or quota limitations according to the hosting party's service policies, although these access limitations must be clearly presented to the user.
- Access through a SPARQL endpoint residing on a public URL and adequately documented.
- File download from Public ftp server redesign on a public address.

3.3.2 Sustainability plan

The Agro-Serv consortium is committed to ensure a long lasting accessibility to its Research Data, and aims at:

Agro-Serv does not enforce specific provisions as long as the data asset is hosted on one of the Acceptable Repositories, however TNA applicants opting for a different hosting solution are expected to take full responsibility of data preservation.

Agro-Serv expects these TNA applicants to illustrate in their Data Management Plan how they intend to secure adequate storage and backup facilities to maintain all the produced data assets after the project's end.

3.4 Making data Interoperable

The Agro-Serv consortium acknowledges the importance of data interoperability: if a data asset cannot be compared, merged, or otherwise integrated with other assets, then its publication would bring little value to the community. The consortium is therefore committed to enforcing data interoperability.

3.4.1 Documentation

Agro-Serv acknowledges the value of documentation for interoperability purposes, and encourages data owners to document their research data assets.

Agro-Serv does not enforce specific provisions on documentation as long as the data asset is hosted on one of the Acceptable Repositories and properly curated according to the repository's best practices, on the other hand TNA applicants opting for a different hosting solution are expected to illustrate in their data management plan how they plan to document their assets.

In such cases, research data itself should not be considered self-documenting and each published asset must be associated with documentation resources accessible through a public URL. Documentation must be browsable and include hypertext references to facilitate its fruition. Recommended documentation formats include markdown, html, and other markup languages. The inclusion of machine-readable documentation including RDF, Open API, and other similar formats where applicable is thoroughly encouraged.

If a scientific publication is tied to the research data asset, the publication itself should be referenced and/or made available as part of the documentation.

3.4.2 Metadata formats and vocabularies

All research data assets produced within the Agro-Serv project must be associated upon publication with appropriate domain specific metadata to allow their integration with third party assets.

Agro-Serv does not enforce specific formats and vocabularies as long as the data asset is hosted on one of the Acceptable Repositories and properly annotated according to the host repository's best practices, however TNA applicants opting for a different hosting solution are expected to describe in their data management plan the metadata annotations they intend to provide for each of their published research data assets.

Acceptable domain specific metadata formats and vocabularies are listed in FAIRsharing, their use is described in RDMkit and the FAIR Cookbook

3.4.3 Data formats and conventions

Agro-Serv requires its TNA beneficiaries to ship their data assets in machine readable formats.

Agro-Serv does not enforce specific formats or conventions as long as the data asset is hosted on one of the Acceptable Repositories and properly formatted according to the host repository's best practices, however TNA applicants opting for a different hosting solution are expected to describe in their data management plan the formats they intend to use to expose their published research data assets.

Examples of acceptable formats include, but are not limited to the ones presented in the following table.

Data type	Suggested format
Tabular data	CSV, international format without comments
Semi-structured data	JSON, XML
Raster grids	NetCDF, GeoTIFF
Vector geographic data	shapefile, GeoJSON, WKT
Textual data	TXT, unicode encoding.

Additionally, the FAIR Cookbook provides extensive documentation on domain-specific formats for omics and other Life Sciences fields.

3.5 Making data Reusable

The Agro-Serv consortium acknowledges the importance of data reusability: if a data asset cannot be reused, its impact on the research community. The consortium is therefore committed to enforcing data reusability.

3.5.1 Licensing

The Agro-Serv project is committed to promote the usage of licences that are broad and permissive in scope, allowing for a wide take-up of publications and therefore easing the spreading of scientific knowledge throughout the research community, and beyond, in compliance with the EU indications and Horizon Europe program recommendations and obligations.

Data assets to be published within the Agro-Serv project and its funded TNA projects will therefore follow one of the following licensing schemes:

- **Single-licensed** with Creative Commons Attribution International Public License version 4 (CC-BY 4.0)⁷.

⁷ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

- **Multi-licensed** with Creative Commons Attribution International Public License version 4 (CC-BY 4.0) and any other licence the author and/or owner is bound to by national provisions and/or other legal and/or contractual constraints when said imposed licences are not equivalent or compatible to CC-BY 4.0.

The Multi-Licence schema should be general enough to apply to a wide variety of situations where hosting platforms may impose more restrictive requirements. However, if the above described licensing options were to prove incompatible with the policies of the data publication venue of choice, TNA applicants suffering from this issue may propose, with adequate explanation, a different licensing schema in their data management plans. The Agro-Serv consortium will then evaluate the request case by case and reserves the right to grant or deny exclusions unilaterally and in a non-challengeable manner.

3.5.2 Provenance

Agro-Serv considers data provenance information instrumental as it facilitates the expression of scientific objectives and protocols to be implemented while respecting the framework of requirements linked to the TNA but also respecting the rules of ethics and data management. The Agro-Serv consortium, therefore, offers its TNA applicants the possibility of acquiring Provenance information via the ISIA application which offers the possibility for platform data managers and their users to collect all the metadata needed to enrich the description of the data production context of their research projects.

Agro-Serv does not enforce specific provisions on data provenance as long as the data asset is hosted on one of the Acceptable Repositories and properly curated according to the repository's best practices, on the other hand TNA applicants opting for a different hosting solution are expected to illustrate in their data management plan how they plan to manage data provenance information.

More specifically, these TNA applicants are expected to present how they plan to associate the metadata collected from the joint design of the project between the platform managers, the evaluation managers and the users with the datasets produced in compliance with all the requirements of the FAIR principles.

4 Ethics, Privacy, and Security

As Agro-Serv will operate in an international context and include multiple stakeholders, ensuring a fair and legal data processing to all assets is of vital importance.

To cope with the different nature of the data assets, methodologies to address ethical requirements as well as data privacy and security are of utmost importance to establish a general framework in this heterogeneous environment.

The General Ethical Guidelines presented in D 9.3 provide such a ethical framework for all Agro-Serv activities, including data management, therefore in this Section we will discuss the practical implementation of the principles thereby expressed on the data management practices, more specifically, the principles and policies used to address a number of privacy and data protection issues raised by the project's activities.

This Section applies to all the data created and/or curated within the Agro-Serv project and its cascading TNA projects, but in particular to data assets containing personal information.

4.1 Data Ethics

As stated in the Agro-Serv Consortium Agreement, results, thereby including all types of data assets, are owned by the Party that generates them.

Whenever it is not possible to establish the respective contribution of each participant to the result or to separate the result itself for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection, the provisions for Joint Ownership (detailed in Grant Agreement Article 8.2 and Article 16.4 and its Annex 5) apply.

Agro-Serv is therefore committed to a fair and transparent management of intellectual property, and condemns all predatory behaviours aimed at superseding, circumventing, or working around the above described data ownership principles.

Furthermore, the Agro-Serv consortium acknowledges that FAIR data and Open data practices should be an instrument to promote reproducible research and knowledge transfer and not means to transfer intellectual property and/or to prevent data owners from exercising their rights.

Should any ethical issue arise within the project's data management perimeter, the general ethical conflict resolution procedures described in the project's General Ethical Guidelines (D 9.3) will be applied.

4.2 Personal data and privacy

Agro-Serv and its participants are committed to guarantee their users a lawful, fair, and transparent personal data processing, as established by Article 5 of the GDPR.

In this Section we address the general principles according to which personal data is collected and gathered within Agro-Serv, and provide a list of the services that will collect and/or process personal data, as well as their relative contact points for further GDPR compliance inquiries.

4.2.1 General principles

Agro-Serv will promote the implementation of several different TNA projects, hence, the project stakeholders (internal and external) as well as the people and organisations affected by the data collection will vary from TNA to TNA. The collection, processing and transmission of personal data will be analysed under principles of:

- The GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679);
- The Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Convention 108 for the Protection of Individuals with regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data
- the national laws applying their provisions.

Any additional regulations at national level that do not fall under the GDPR and apply to data protection or any other sensitive information will also be taken into account.

Agro-Serv is committed to respecting the privacy of all stakeholders and involved personnel. Whenever a project-related activity will deal with personal data, its compliance with the above mentioned regulations will be investigated.

4.2.2 Why personal data get collected

Agro-Serv collects personal data to be able to:

- Produce contracts in the form of TNA project grants, therein including proposal evaluation.
- Erogate services to researchers participating in funded TNA projects (WP 1).
- Produce clear indications of authorship and copyright for published data assets, thereby including all forms of citation.
- Contact directly TNA applicants and data asset owners and/or copyright holders for important communications including, but not limited to: required actions, approaching deadlines, proposal evaluation results, and policy updates.
- Track impact of consortium activities and produce evidence of said impact for project stakeholders (WP5 and WP 6).

Additionally, the RI offering TNA and VA may collect personal data for further purposes in compliance with the Ethical Guidelines provided by D9.3.

In such a case, the additional finalities of personal data collection will be presented in the TNA or VA conditions, in a clear and intelligible way to the interested data subjects before the data collection would take place.

4.2.3 Personal data Agro-Serv collects

Upon registering to one of the Agro-Serv services users may be required to produce a username, a password, and a valid email address to activate their personal account. Additionally, users may choose to provide Agro-Serv with additional personal information such as affiliation, telephone number, and address.

Agro-Serv collects content created or uploaded by users while using its services, such as grant applications, and scientific data and metadata. It is under the responsibility of those who provide such data to make sure it does not disclose third-party data without explicit consent.

Whenever Agro-Serv contacts a TNA applicant/data owner/data copyright holder or vice versa, Agro-Serv will keep record of the interaction.

4.2.4 Personal data collected by Services and TNAs

Individual members of the Agro-Serv consortium may supply additional services to TNA projects which may require personal data collection and/or collect third parties personal data within initiatives funded by TNA grants. The responsibility of a lawful and ethical personal data management lies upon the partner owning the service, however the Agro-Serv consortium requires to be informed of the modalities and finalities of personal data collection.

Before activation, each service and TNA is expected to provide the consortium with a Ethical Self-Assessment detailing the planned personal data collection, storage, and processing activities. The Ethical Self-Assessment checklist and executive form are made available through the ISIA platform and its fulfilment is a mandatory step in the TNA application process.

TNA applicants are encouraged to refer to the consortium DPOs, whose contacts are provided in Appendix 1, for any inquiry about regulations in force within the platforms they intend to include in their TNA activities.

4.2.5 Consent management and data subject rights

In accordance with the GDPR's provisions, data subjects must be able to express consent to data collection and processing explicitly, as their consent cannot be taken for granted under any circumstance. Similarly, data subjects must be provided with the means to exercise their rights on the data they provided the consortium with.

The Agro-Serv consortium expects each partner and each TNA beneficiary to manage user consent and to administer access to the fundamental data subject rights in accordance with their institution's guidelines and best practices. The Agro-Serv consortium will not enforce additional policies and/or constraints on its member and/or related organisations as long as significant incompatibilities with the consortium's General Ethical Guidelines described in D 9.3 emerge, in such a case the ethical conflict resolution procedures described in the same document (D 9.3) will be applied.

TNA applicants are encouraged to refer to the consortium DPOs, whose contacts are provided in Appendix 1, for any inquiry about regulations in force within the platforms they intend to include in their TNA activities.

In the unlikely event of a TNA applicant not having a consent management and data subject rights administration policy to refer to, the Agro-Serv consortium expects the TNA applicant to produce one and to include it in the application. Such custom policy must include an example of consent form to be administered to data subjects (a model template is proposed in Appendix 2) and a clear explanation of how they intend to allow their data subjects to exercise their fundamental rights (namely: the right to be informed, the right of access, the right to rectification, the right to erasure/be forgotten, the right to restrict processing, the right to data portability, and the right to object) as established by the GDPR.

4.3 Security

In accordance with the GDPR's provisions, and data management best practices, the Agro-Serv consortium expects its partners and TNA beneficiaries to adopt a security-by-design approach concerning personal data management to prevent and/or pose significant obstacles to all forms of data breach.

The Agro-Serv consortium does not enforce specific provisions on data security, but nevertheless expects all its partners and TNA beneficiaries to comply with their parent institution's policies and best practices, therefore the Agro-Serv consortium declines any responsibility on data breaches and/or data losses.

Nevertheless, the Agro-Serv consortium expects to be informed of potential data breach risks within its funded activities' perimeter, and therefore TNA applicants whose activities include personal data management are expected to provide in the Ethical self-assessment details on how they plan to secure their data assets and which measures they intend to implement to avoid data breaches and/or losses.

TNA applicants are encouraged to refer to the consortium DPOs, whose contacts are provided in Appendix 1, for any inquiry about regulations in force within the platforms they intend to include in their TNA activities.

Appendix

A1 Data Protection Officers

In this appendix we provide, for each legal entity processing personal data within Agro-Serv, contact information to reach out to Data Protection Officers.

Not all beneficiaries have a formal DPO, however we can provide reference to responsible acting functionally as DPOs

Beneficiary	DPO name	contact
AnaEE		
CNR		
CNRs		
CREA	Valentina Longo	valentina.longo@crea.gov.it
INRAe		

A2 consent form Example

Required by European Union General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 ("GDPR")

To Be Signed By Individual Providing Personal Data

[Institution Name] is the controller of your personal data. You may contact [Institution Name] at [address] or by phone and email at: [Insert Name and Contact Info of Person in Unit Requesting Personal Data].

Your personal data will be used for the following purposes (check all that apply):

- marketing academic programs;
- communicating University activities and accomplishments;
- soliciting donations;
- recruiting students;
- recruiting employees;

research;
 Other [include detailed description of use of personal data].

The categories of personal data you are being asked to consent to [Institution Name]’s collection and use are your name, address, email address, telephone number and [include description of any other personal data collected].

[Institution Name] will share your personal data with third party software providers who collect, store and process your personal data on behalf of the University and who are contractually obligated to keep your personal data confidential subject to appropriate safeguards to prevent it from unauthorised disclosure.

[Institution Name] also intends to share your personal data with: [identify all units and third parties that will receive personal data].

Your personal data will be stored in accordance with the record retention requirements applicable to [Institution Name] as a public research institution of [your country].

Under the GDPR, you have the right to request access to, rectify, erase and restrict the processing of your personal data. You also have the right to revoke this consent to use your personal data. If you feel [Institution Name] has violated the GDPR, you have the right to file a complaint with the appropriate EU supervisory authority.

Please [sign/electronically sign/check box below], date and return by [email/submit] the below:

I consent to [Institution Name] using my personal data for the purposes described in this notice and understand that I can withdraw my consent at any time.

gives consent does not give consent

Name of Individual providing Consent:	
Address of Individual providing Consent:	
Signature:	Date of Signature: